

Rhoifolin potentiates the anti-cancer activity of doxorubicin in MDA-MB-231 triple-negative breast cancer cells

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Abstract

Background: The combination of chemotherapeutic agents with natural compounds has gained attention as a strategy to improve treatment effectiveness and reduce adverse effects of cancer therapies. This study investigates the potential use of rhoifolin, a citrus-derived flavonoid, to sensitize triple-negative breast cancer cells (MDA-MB-231) to doxorubicin.

Materials and methods: The cytotoxicity of rhoifolin, doxorubicin, and their combination was assessed via MTT assay. Cell migration and proliferation were evaluated through scratch and colony formation assays, respectively. Caspase 3, Bax, and Bcl-2 gene expression were analyzed to explore apoptotic mechanisms.

Results: The IC₅₀ values were 6.22 μM for doxorubicin and 102 μM for rhoifolin. Rhoifolin significantly enhanced doxorubicin's cytotoxic effect with a combination index <1 at various ratios. At a dose of 50 μM rhoifolin, the anti-migratory effect of 1.5 μM doxorubicin was significantly increased ($p < 0.01$). The combination reduced colony formation to 72.5 ± 8.5 colonies compared to 202 ± 9 in the control group. Moreover, the combination increased caspase 3 gene expression by 22.2-fold.

Conclusion: Rhoifolin potentiated the anti-cancer effects of doxorubicin, suggesting its potential as an adjuvant therapy in cancer.

Keywords

caspase 3, cytotoxicity, doxorubicin, migration, rhoifolin, triple-negative breast cancer

Introduction

Cancer continues to be a major global health challenge, driving the need for the ongoing development of effective therapeutic approaches. Chemotherapy remains a corner-

stone of cancer treatment, but its effectiveness is often limited by systemic toxicity and the development of drug resistance (Elfadadny et al. 2023). Triple-negative breast cancer constitutes 24% of newly diagnosed breast cancer cases and is characterized by the absence of hormone receptor expres-

sion and HER2 gene amplification (Borri and Granaglia 2021). This aggressive type of breast cancer poses treatment challenges due to the lack of distinct molecular therapeutic targets and its tendency for metastasis (Abbas et al. 2024).

Doxorubicin (Dox), an anthracycline antibiotic, is widely used for treating various malignancies due to its potent cytotoxic effects and is recognized as one of the most effective treatments for breast cancer (Sritharan and Sivalingam 2021). However, its clinical application is frequently limited by dose-dependent cardiotoxicity and the development of drug resistance (Elfadadny et al. 2023; Al-Sahlawi et al. 2024; Al-Samydai et al. 2024).

The integration of chemotherapeutic agents with natural compounds has gained attention as a promising strategy to improve treatment effectiveness and reduce adverse side effects (Staedler et al. 2011). Recent studies suggest that natural products such as flavonoids can modulate the activity of chemotherapeutic agents, potentially enhancing their efficacy while reducing toxicity (Elfadadny et al. 2023). Rhoifolin – apigenin-7-O-β-neohesperidoside – is found in citrus plants (Gandhi et al. 2020) and in the Chinese anti-cancer plant *Callicarpa nudiflora* (Xiong et al. 2021). This flavonoid has attracted attention for its diverse pharmacological properties, including anti-inflammatory, anticancer, anti-diabetic, hepatoprotective, antimicrobial, and antihypertensive effects (Refaat et al. 2015). Rhoifolin was selected in this study as a modulator of the chemotherapeutic activity of Dox. Its natural origin and lack of cytotoxic activity against healthy normal cells (Vero cells) (Eldahshan 2013) make it an attractive candidate for combination therapy, particularly with chemotherapeutic agents like Dox.

The ability of flavonoids to enhance the therapeutic efficacy of traditional drugs while reducing their side effects aligns with the goal of developing safer, more effective cancer treatments. Understanding the synergistic effects could pave the way for more effective combination therapies with improved therapeutic indices. Therefore, this study was designed to explore the potential of rhoifolin to sensitize triple-negative breast cancer cells to Dox. The effect of this combination was tested on cellular proliferation, cell migration, colony formation, and apoptotic activity. By investigating the combination of Dox and rhoifolin, this study seeks to harness the complementary properties of these compounds, potentially overcoming the limitations of single-agent therapies.

Materials and methods

Cells and culture media

MDA-MB-231 triple-negative breast cancer cells were obtained from the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC). MDA-MB-231 cells (passage number 22) were cultivated as monolayer cultures in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium (DMEM) (Euroclone, Italy) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS) (Gibco, Germany) and penicillin and streptomycin (Euroclone, Italy) (100 U/mL) at 37 °C in a humidified 5% CO₂ atmosphere.

Cell proliferation assay

The MTT (3-(4,5-dimethylthiazolyl)-2,5-diphenyl-tetrazolium bromide) test (Promega, USA) relies on the capacity of mitochondrial dehydrogenase to convert MTT into a purple formazan product. This test was employed to assess the cytotoxic effect and calculate the IC₅₀ (half maximal inhibitory concentration) of rhoifolin (Biosynth Carbosynth, UK) and Dox (Biosynth Carbosynth, UK). MDA-MB-231 cells cultured in DMEM were placed into a 96-well plate and incubated at 37 °C in 5% CO₂ for 24 h to attach to the wells after initial seeding. A range of drug concentrations was prepared freshly in DMEM by serial dilution from the stock concentration and vortexed thoroughly to ensure complete dissolution. A stock solution of rhoifolin was prepared by dissolving it in DMSO. All experiments were performed in triplicate. The final concentration of DMSO did not exceed 1%. Following 72 h of drug exposure, MTT cell viability was assessed using the following formula:

$$\% \text{ Cell viability} = \frac{(\text{OD}_{\text{sample}} - \text{OD}_{\text{blank}})}{(\text{OD}_{\text{vehicle}} - \text{OD}_{\text{blank}})} \times 100\%$$

Combination index

Synergy evaluation of Dox and rhoifolin was determined by calculating the CI according to the method described by Chou and Talalay using the CompuSyn software (ComboSyn Inc., USA, version 1.0), which is freely available online from the website (<https://compusyn.software.informer.com/1.0/>). Fixed ratios of 1:2, 1:4, and 1:8 of Dox-to-rhoifolin were used.

Cell migration

A scratch (wound healing) assay was performed as follows: MDA-MB-231 cells were seeded to nearly complete confluence in a monolayer in a 12-well plate. After 24 h of seeding, a sterile plastic pipette tip was used to produce a wound (scratch), and then treatment was added. Finally, cells were cultured in DMEM at 5% CO₂ and 37 °C. Treatment was done by adding Dox, rhoifolin, or a combination of both. After 0 and 72 h, the plate was photographed using a Nikon microscope camera (Japan). The area of the wound was calculated by the equation scratch closure = $[(A_0 - A_t) / A_0] \times 100$, where A₀ represents the area at zero time and A_t the area after 72 h. All treatments were done in triplicate. Doses of rhoifolin and Dox were set at half their respective IC₅₀ values.

Colony-forming assay

MDA-MB-231 cells were seeded in 12-well plates at a density of 600 cells per well and incubated overnight to ensure proper attachment. Following incubation, treatments were applied using Dox, rhoifolin, or their combination. After treatment, cells were fixed with 4% paraformaldehyde for 1 h and stained with 0.1% crystal violet solution to visualize and quantify the resulting colonies. Vehicle-treated

cells served as a negative control. All treatments were performed in triplicate. The doses of rhoifolin and Dox were chosen to be half of the IC_{50} of each compound.

Gene expression of caspase 3, Bcl-2, and Bax genes

RNA extraction and quantitative real-time polymerase chain reaction (qPCR) were performed as follows: MDA-MB-231 cells (1×10^6) were cultured in DMEM medium. After 24 h, the culture medium was replaced with a fresh one, and treatments with Dox, rhoifolin, or their combination were applied.

Gene expression analysis was conducted 72 h post-treatment. The cells were washed with PBS, scraped, and total RNA was extracted using the Quick-RNA Mini-prep Kit (Zymo, USA; Cat. #R1055) following the manufacturer's protocol. One microgram of total RNA from treated or vehicle-treated cells was used for cDNA synthesis, performed with the ProtoScript kit (BioLabs; Cat. #E6300S) on a 2720 Thermal Cycler (Applied Biosystems, USA). The GAPDH gene served as an internal control. qPCR was carried out using TB Green Master Mix (Takara, Japan; Cat. #RR82LR) and a QuantStudio5 system (Applied Biosystems by Thermo Fisher). The cycling conditions were as follows: an initial denaturation at 95 °C for 30 seconds (1 cycle), followed by 40 cycles of denaturation at 95 °C for 5 seconds, annealing at 62 °C (for GAPDH and caspase-3) or 65.5 °C (for Bcl-2 and Bax) for 60 seconds, and extension at 72 °C for 60 seconds. A melting curve analysis was subsequently performed from 60 °C to 95 °C. Primers were synthesized by Macrogen (South Korea), and the sequences for sense and antisense primers of GAPDH, caspase 3, Bcl-2, and Bax are detailed in Table 1. Gene expression levels were normalized by calculating the ratio of the target gene to GAPDH for each sample.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using GraphPad Prism version 8, in which a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted for all tested parameters. Following the ANOVA, Tukey's post-hoc test was performed. Significance was determined at a threshold of $p < 0.05$. Experimental results were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD).

Results

Cell proliferation assay

The half-maximal inhibitory concentrations (IC_{50}) of Dox and rhoifolin against the MDA-MB-231 cancer cell line after 72 h of treatment were 6.22 μ M and 102 μ M, respectively. Various ratios of the rhoifolin-Dox combination were evaluated for their effects on cell viability, as shown in Table 2. At a 1:2 ratio, the combination index (CI) values calculated using CompuSyn software indicated syner-

gistic interactions, with CI values ranging from 0.024 to 0.883. A similar pattern was observed for the 1:4 and 1:8 ratios, with CI values consistently below 1. These results demonstrated that CI values at all effect levels were consistently less than 1, confirming synergy.

The 1:8 ratio of Dox to rhoifolin was the most effective combination, offering strong synergy, enhanced efficacy, and significant dose reduction benefits. This suggests that rhoifolin may help sensitize triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC) cells to Dox, potentially lowering the required therapeutic dose and reducing side effects in future clinical applications (Table 2).

Fig. 1 illustrates the dose-response relationship for the rhoifolin-Dox combination across three different ratios. A flat sigmoidal curve ($m < 1$) was observed for both Dox and rhoifolin, with linear correlation coefficients (r) of approximately 0.95 for the 1:2 ratio, 0.97 for the 1:4 ratio, and 0.99 for the 1:8 ratio. In addition, the combination index (CI) plot shows values below 1 for the three drug ratios (1:2, 1:4, and 1:8), indicating a synergistic effect with Dox (Fig. 1).

Cell migration

The effect of the rhoifolin-Dox combination on cell migration was evaluated. Following 72 h of treatment, the wound closure area was 16.5 \pm 8.0% in cells treated with 3 μ M Dox combined with 50 μ M rhoifolin, compared to 99.2 \pm 0.11% in the control group and 24 \pm 8.0% in cells treated with Dox alone (Figs 2, 3). At a dose of 50 μ M, rhoifolin potentiated the anti-migratory effect of 1.5 μ M Dox with a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.01$) between Dox alone (closure area = 63.6 \pm 11.6%) and the rhoifolin-Dox combination (closure area = 27.6 \pm 4.6%), despite the fact that 50 μ M rhoifolin alone had no significant anti-migratory effect compared to the control.

Colony-forming assay

The colony-forming assay was used to evaluate cell survival by assessing the ability of single cells to form colonies. As shown in Fig. 4, a large number of colonies (202 \pm 9 colonies) was observed in cells treated with vehicle (control). By contrast, treatment with 50 μ M rhoifolin resulted in a significant decrease in colony number (72.5 \pm 8.5). All tested Dox doses (0.75–6 μ M), as well as all rhoifolin-Dox combinations (3 μ M Dox + 50 μ M rhoifolin, 1.5 μ M Dox + 50 μ M rhoifolin, and 0.75 μ M Dox + 50 μ M rhoifolin), completely inhibited colony formation.

Effect of rhoifolin/Dox on the expression of genes involved in apoptosis

Dox (3 μ M) increased caspase 3 gene expression by 5-fold. However, when 3 μ M Dox was combined with 50 μ M rhoifolin, a 111-fold increase in caspase 3 gene expression was recorded (22.2% increase). Similarly, the combination of 3 μ M Dox and 50 μ M rhoifolin significantly increased Bax and Bcl-2 gene expression compared to 3 μ M Dox alone (Fig. 5).

Table 1. Sequences of primers.

Gene	Sequence of primer
<i>BAX</i>	Forward: 5'-TGGAGCTGCAGAGGATGATG -3' Reverse: 5'- TGCCACTCGGAAAAAGACCT -3'
<i>BCL-2</i>	Forward: 5'-AAG CCG GCG ACG ACT TCT-3' Reverse: 5'-GGT GCC GGT TCA GGT ACT-3'
<i>Caspase-3</i>	Forward: 5'-AGCAAACCTCAGGGAAACATT-3' Reverse: 5'-CTCAGAAGCACACAAAACAAACT-3'
<i>GAPDH</i>	Forward: 5'- TGTTGCCATCAATGACCCCTTC-3' Reverse: 5'-CTCCACGACGTACTIONACTCAGCGC-3'

Table 2. Synergistic interaction between Dox and rhoifolin. The combination index (CI) and dose reduction index (DRI) are illustrated at different concentration ratios.

Ratio	Fa	CI	Dose Dox	Dose Rhoifolin	DRI Dox	DRI Rhoifolin
1:8	0.9	0.039	43.49	347.93	25.77	1110.51
	0.75	0.032	6.40	51.25	33.68	313.68
	0.5	0.034	0.94	7.54	44.03	88.60
1:4	0.9	0.068	75.90	303.00	14.76	1272.57
	0.75	0.032	6.72	26.86	32.13	598.47
	0.5	0.017	0.59	2.37	69.93	281.45
1:2	0.9	0.356	83.15	167.19	2.83	257.00
	0.75	0.094	5.68	11.37	10.75	891.17
	0.5	0.024	0.39	0.77	40.80	3090.13

Figure 1. Dose-effect response curves for Dox, rhoifolin, and their combination (Comb). **A** 1:2 Dox-to-Rhoifolin ratio **B** 1:4 Dox-to-rhoifolin ratio **C** 1:8 Dox-to-rhoifolin ratio. Combination index plots for 1:2 Dox-to-rhoifolin ratio (**D**), 1:4 Dox-to-rhoifolin ratio (**E**), and 1:8 Dox-to-rhoifolin ratio (**F**). The dose-effect curves and combination index plots were generated using CompuSyn software, with values representing the mean of three independent experiments. Color code: Green: combination of Dox and rhoifolin; Blue: Dox alone; Red: rhoifolin alone.

	At 0 time	After 72 h
3 μ M Dox		
50 μ M Rhoifolin		
Combination		
Control (vehicle only)		

Figure 2. Photomicrographs showing the effect of Dox, rhoifolin, and their combination on MDA-MB-231 migration after 72 h.

Figure 3. Effect of Dox, rhoifolin, and their combinations on MDA-MB-231 cell migration. Each experiment was conducted in triplicate. Data are presented as mean \pm SD. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$, **** $p < 0.0001$.

Figure 4. Representative images of MDA-MB-231 breast cancer cell colonies. **A** Cells with 3 μ M of Dox **B** cells with 50 μ M of rhoifolin (Rh) **C** cells treated with a combination (COMB) of 3 μ M Dox and 50 μ M rhoifolin, and **D** cells treated with vehicle (control; CNT). The experiment was conducted in triplicate.

Figure 5. Gene expression of caspase 3, Bax, and Bcl-2 produced by Dox alone, rhoifolin, or their combination. Each experiment was conducted in triplicate. Data are presented as mean \pm SD. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$, **** $p < 0.0001$.

Discussion

Studies in drug discovery revealed that many phytochemicals have anticancer effects. The IC_{50} of rhoifolin after 72 h against MDA-MB-231 cells is reported here for the first time, and it was found to be 102 μM , which is equivalent to 59.0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. In a previous study, *Cirsium setidens* extract, containing rhoifolin as a major compound, efficiently suppressed the growth of breast cancer cells while leaving normal cell growth unaffected (Park et al. 2023). Rhoifolin demonstrated an anticancer effect against various cancer cell lines, including human epidermoid larynx (Hep 2) ($IC_{50} = 5.9 \mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) and human cervical (HeLa) carcinoma cell lines ($IC_{50} = 6.2 \mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$). Anticancer activities were also obtained against hepatocellular (Hep G2) ($IC_{50} = 22.6 \mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$), colon (HCT-116) ($IC_{50} = 34.8 \mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$), fetal human lung fibroblast (MRC-5) carcinoma ($IC_{50} = 44.6 \mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) (Eldahshan 2013), and pancreatic cell line ($IC_{50} = 100 \mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) (Zheng et al. 2022). This indicates that the anticancer effect of rhoifolin is cell-specific. A notable aspect of rhoifolin was its lack of cytotoxic activity against healthy normal cells (Vero cells), indicating a high level of selectivity for targeting cancer cells (Eldahshan 2013).

Combination therapy has emerged as a promising approach to enhance the efficacy of chemotherapy while reducing its side effects (Elfadadny et al. 2023). Despite possessing a non-potent cytotoxic effect against triple-negative breast cancer cells, rhoifolin demonstrated a significant synergistic effect when combined with Dox. In comparison, the citrus flavanone glycoside hesperidin exerted synergistic effects dose-dependently, and it was able to synergistically amplify the cytotoxic effect of Dox (Amalina et al. 2023). Similarly, a non-toxic dosage of the flavonoid quercetin enhanced the cytotoxic effect of Dox on MCF-7 and MDA-MB-231 breast cancer cells while decreasing the cytotoxic impact of Dox on normal mammary and myocardial cells (Li et al. 2018).

In the present study, Dox demonstrated a significant inhibitory effect on the migration in the MDA-MB-231 cell line, which agrees with previous studies (Hulkower and Herber 2011). Furthermore, rhoifolin was able to hinder cell migration in a dose-dependent manner for both MDA-MB-231 and MDA-MB-468 cell lines (Hulkower and Herber 2011; Xiong et al. 2021). These results are compatible with our findings.

A clear observation from the present work was that Dox was able to completely prevent MDA-MB-231 colony formation, while 50 μM rhoifolin reduced them significantly. A previous investigation found that both Dox and *Citrus aurantium* peel extract, which contains rhoifolin as a major component, induced cell cycle arrest (Suzery et al. 2023). It has been reported that Dox alone is able to increase the percentage of apoptotic cells in MDA-MB 231 up to 51% (Sabzichi et al. 2019). This agrees with the findings of this study that Dox significantly increased the expression of caspase 3.

Rhoifolin (50 μM , equivalent to 59 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) in our study was not able to increase the expression of caspase 3. Other

studies reported that a relatively high dose of rhoifolin (0.5 mg/mL) promoted apoptosis in pancreatic cancer cells (Zheng et al. 2022). This may indicate that rhoifolin can induce apoptosis at high concentrations, or its effect is cell line dependent. Fortunately, a synergistic effect between rhoifolin and Dox was achieved by increasing the expression of caspase 3 by 22.2-fold compared to Dox alone. Consistent with the reported literature that Dox enhances caspase expression in MDA-MB-231 cells (Mahdavi et al. 2024), thereby promoting the apoptotic pathway.

To sum up, the potentiation of Dox's effects by rhoifolin can be explained through multiple mechanisms that enhance its cytotoxicity, inhibit cancer progression, and promote apoptosis in TNBC cells. These mechanisms include (1) synergistic cytotoxicity: the combination of rhoifolin and Dox significantly decreased the IC_{50} value, indicating that rhoifolin enhances the drug's ability to kill cancer cells more effectively at lower doses. This may be due to interference with survival pathways. In pancreatic cancer cells, rhoifolin inhibited proliferation and promoted apoptosis, which was accompanied by upregulation of JNK and p-JNK as well as downregulation of p-AKT (Zheng et al. 2022). (2) Apoptosis induction via caspase 3 activation: Caspase 3 is a key executioner of apoptosis, leading to DNA fragmentation and cell dismantling. Dox exerted apoptotic effects in the MDA-MB 231 cell line by upregulating Bax, caspase 8, and caspase 3 and downregulating Bcl-2 protein expression (Pilco-Ferreto and Calaf 2016). In addition, Dox induced G2/M and sub-G1 cell cycle arrest (Suzery et al. 2023). The 22.2-fold increase in caspase 3 gene expression when rhoifolin was combined with Dox suggests that rhoifolin may promote apoptosis, making cancer cells more susceptible to Dox-induced cell death. However, higher concentrations of rhoifolin may be required to achieve this effect independently. (3) Inhibition of cell migration and proliferation: rhoifolin significantly enhanced the anti-migratory effects of Dox, reducing the ability of TNBC cells to spread. Additionally, the combination therapy decreased colony formation, indicating a suppression of tumorigenic potential. In a previous study, rhoifolin was found to inhibit ezrin phosphorylation, consequently disrupting its interaction with podocalyxin-like protein 1 (PODXL). Additionally, this compound exhibited a distinct inhibitory effect on transforming growth factor-beta 1 (TGF- β 1)-induced EMT in MDA-MB-231 cells (Xiong et al. 2021).

It is worth noting that investigating the impact of rhoifolin on the multiple drug resistance (MDR1, P-glycoprotein) efflux pump using a Dox-resistant cell line remains an important research avenue. However, in the present study, it is unlikely that rhoifolin exerted its effects through MDR1 inhibition since wild-type MDA-MB-231 cells generally exhibit low or absent MDR1 expression, though it can be induced under selective chemotherapy pressure. Previous studies have shown that rhoifolin was able to inhibit vinblastine transport. However, it enhanced daunorubicin transport in the human pancreatic adenocarcinoma cell line Panc-1 (Hu and Morris 2004). Another study demonstrated that rhoifolin can modulate mul-

tidrug resistance-associated protein 1 (MRP1)-mediated drug transport of daunomycin and vinblastine in Panc-1 (Nguyen et al. 2003).

Conclusion

The potential of combining chemotherapeutic drugs with natural compounds, such as flavonoids, represents a promising avenue. Rhoifolin, a naturally derived flavonoid, has demonstrated notable anticancer activity and the ability to modulate proliferation, migration, and apoptosis, all of which are critical in cancer progression and chemotherapy resistance. This study addresses a critical gap in understanding how natural compounds can be effectively integrated with conventional chemotherapy.

This study holds significant importance in the ongoing quest to improve cancer treatment outcomes by enhancing the chemosensitivity of chemotherapeutic agents such as Dox. Their clinical use is often constrained by severe side effects, including cardiotoxicity and the development of multidrug resistance in cancer cells.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

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The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

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Author contributions

A.K., M.A., and M.A.-Q. conceived and supervised the project. A.A.-R., R.M., and R.O. performed the experiments, and A.A.-R. and M.A. wrote the manuscript. A.K. and M.A.-Q. critically analyzed the results. All authors read and approved the finalized article.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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